

PARALLEL ANT COLONY OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM FOR EFFICIENT CLOUD COMPUTING CONTAINER ALLOCATION

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ABSTRACT

Containers have completely changed how modern applications are designed and delivered by offering an extremely modular, scalable, and efficient environment. Scheduling and allocating resources—like CPU, memory, and network bandwidth—into containerized cloud computing environments is a challenging operation. Optimization strategies mitigate these issues by guaranteeing optimal resource utilization, lowering operational expenses, and improving overall system performance. A popular swarm intelligence technique for addressing optimization issues is Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), which is motivated from the social dynamics of ant colonies. Resources utilization in container cloud computing environments should be made efficient while maintaining high performance and scalability by combining the advantages of parallel computing with the strengths of ACO. To increase efficiency when dealing with big and complex issue cases, parallel computing techniques are typically used. This enables ACO strategies to produce excellent results in realistic execution times, while taking on challenging optimization problems among the utilization of containers, virtual machines, and hosts. This paper explores the use of the Parallel Ant Colony Optimization (PACO) technique for containers in a cloud computing environment to improve load balancing, optimize resource allocation, and achieve higher levels of scalability and energy efficiency. The suggested method shows great promise for streamlining cloud operations through the use of parallelism, a decrease in computational overhead, and an enhancement in overall system performance. The experimental findings demonstrate that the proposed method outperforms the MACO and FCFS algorithms with regard to the execution time and the throughput. Also it keeps a considerable improvement in resource utilization between virtual and physical computers.

Keywords: Containers, Virtual Machines, Optimization Techniques, Ant Colony Optimization, Cloud Computing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Containers [1] have emerged as a key component of cloud computing due to their lightweight, portable, and effective method of packaging and deploying applications. A difficult optimization challenge in cloud computing environments is the containerized scheduling and virtual machine placement problem. They have a big impact on how resources are used in a cluster, which can therefore affect the environment and operating expenses. The scientific community keeps looking for novel optimization approaches which can outperform the conventional exact procedures, which are frequently rendered ineffective for addressing difficult real-life optimization issues in reasonable amounts of time due to their high computational requirements. Given this, nature-inspired metaheuristic techniques have become adaptable and reliable tools for resolving NP-hard optimization issues, taking advantage of their capacity to calculate precise solutions in reasonable execution durations. Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) [2] is population-based metaheuristic depends on swarm intelligence and inspired by the social behavior of ant colonies, the algorithm solves real-world optimization problems efficiently by utilizing the fundamental ideas of distributed partnership, self-organizing, adaptation, and dispersal that are present in ant communities [3]. The idea behind Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) stems from the way ants navigate their environment to find a way to get food for their colony. Ants behave quite simply in the natural world. With ACO, artificial "ants" create solutions to optimization issues and gradually improve them based on pheromone trails. This probabilistic technique is inspired by the foraging behavior of ants. They leave pheromone trails behind as they travel aimlessly in search of food before returning to their colony. When more ants discover the trail, they are more likely to follow it rather than continue to wander as previously. If the trail is successfully followed, the following ants might also reinforce it. Therefore, when one ant finds a favorable route from the colony to a food supply, there's a greater chance that additional ants will follow it, and positive reinforcement eventually leads to all the ants taking the same way.

The resources utilization in containerized cloud computing environments may be made efficient while maintaining high performance and scalability by combining the advantages of parallel computing with the strengths of ACO. This approach is known as Parallel Ant Colony Optimization (PACO), and it is a potent method for resolving challenging optimization problems. The goal of Parallel Ant Colony Optimization (PACO), an enhanced variant of the ACO algorithm, is to tackle complicated optimization problems more effectively by utilizing parallel computing. PACO improves the speed since using parallelism PACO can drastically cut down on the amount of time needed to find solutions that are optimal or nearly optimal. It distributes the computing load so it can handle more complicated and large-scale issues than standard ACO so it improves the scalability of the system. Parallel colonies can preserve a higher degree of solution diversity, decreasing the chance of early convergence to suboptimal solutions. Parallel Ant Colony Optimization can be done in different strategies as shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Parallel ACO Strategies.

- Multiple Ant Colonies [4]: Several ant colonies can operate concurrently in PACO, each investigating a distinct region of the solution space. To increase overall convergence, these colonies can exchange information regularly, such as pheromone updates.
- Data Parallelism [5]: It is possible to divide the work of simulating several ants in a single colony among several processors or cores. This expedites the search process by enabling multiple ants to investigate various trails at the same time.
- Task Parallelism [6]: It is possible to carry out various ACO process steps (solution development and pheromone update) concurrently. For example, one processor may be developing new solutions while another manages pheromone updates.
- Hybrid Parallelism [7]: It combines several parallel techniques, like managing several colonies concurrently and parallelizing the ant activities in each colony.

This work proposes PACO, based on data parallelism, to increase the resource utilization rate for virtual machines (VMs) and containers, while also improving load balancing and reducing resource execution times. The PACO technique is compared to the MACO [8] and FCFS in terms of execution time and maintains significant improvement of the resource utilization among containers and VMs. More accurately, the main contribution of this work could be summed up as follows:

- a) Introduces a novel taxonomy for PACO strategies
- b) Implements a parallel ant colony optimization technique for efficient container allocation in a cloud-computing environment
- c) Comparing the result of the PACO algorithm with the MACO, and FCFS algorithms.

This paper is formatted as follows: The related work is presented in Section II. Section III presents the MACO algorithm. Section IV discusses the proposed PACO algorithm for container allocation in the cloud computing environment. Section V describes the simulation results and the implementation environment. Finally, Section VI covers the conclusion and future work.

II. RELATED WORK

This section reviews the current studies that use the parallel ant colony optimization technique for virtual machine allocation in cloud computing environments. Joshua Peake et al. [8] describe an improved Virtual Machine Placement (VMP) strategy that efficiently makes use of parallelization techniques and modern processor capabilities. The algorithm combines a conventional ACO version with well-known parallelization techniques and SIMD vector operations. An advantageous feature of the Max-Min Ant System (MMAS) form of

ACO is its parallelization due to the lack of communication between ants during iteration. The disadvantage of this work is that they don't use the parallel ACO for container allocation.

To solve the scheduling problem for parallel machines, Claudia R. Gatica et al. [9] used an Ant Colony System (ACS) that was developed from the ACO metaheuristic. It is significant to remember that the ant algorithms' primary means of effectively searching the search space are the pheromone trail and heuristic data. Several heuristic values, including Least Slack (SLACK), Earliest Due Date (EDD), Longest Processing Time (LPT), and Shortest Processing Time (SPT) were taken into consideration when implementing the ACS for the scheduling problem examined in this paper. A comparison of earlier outcomes from basic genetic algorithms (GAs) and proof of the ACO metaheuristic enhanced performance on this specific scheduling challenge are also presented. The experiments were based on a study of twenty instances, for each of the three difficulties, in which the goal was to minimize the parallel identical machine scheduling problems. The ANOVA test was utilized to statistically analyze the results. The lack of consideration for the use of ACO in container allocation is a drawback of this work. They intend to use hybridization techniques to provide local search to the Ant Colony System.

Jian Si et al. [10] focused on the study of the ACO algorithm based on the path planning problem for mobile robots in a complicated environment. A unique parallel ACO (PACO) method was presented to address the issues of low search efficiency, vulnerability to deadlocks, and local optimum for the standard ACO technique. A unique parallel ACO method was presented to address the issues of low search efficiency, vulnerability to deadlocks, and local optimum in the standard ACO algorithm. To balance exploration space with convergence speed, the algorithm developed a rank-based pheromone updating mechanism. To solve the stalemate issue, it also devised a hybrid strategy that combines killing directly with ongoing work. Additionally, the technique first determined a suitable position for splitting the primary problem into two smaller problems, which were then addressed using MATLAB's single program multiple data (SPMD) parallel programming technique to efficiently realize the path planning in complicated surroundings. Simulation testing demonstrated that the suggested algorithm's efficacy was confirmed. Applying the PACO algorithm to pertinent procedures can conserve computational resources and give managers quicker, more accurate solutions for making decisions. This is because the technique can significantly cut computation time while maintaining solution accuracy. One goal of future research is to create a more effective decomposition technique that divides the original problem into two or more smaller problems, each of which may be tackled as evenly and concurrently as possible. The drawback of their work is that they didn't address the path-planning problem in dynamic environments.

Yasameen A. Ghani Alyouzbak et al. [11] describe a novel method that, in comparison to the widely used TESA technique for cloud load balancing, relies on the ACO strategy to decrease the cloud energy usage and execution time. Z. Zeng et al. [12] aim to enhance ant colony optimization (ACO) in light of the issues with parameter sensitivity, local optimum, and sluggish convergence that are well-known. They present a fully parallel ACO (FP-ACO) to efficiently address the traveling salesman problem (TSP). They start a pheromone compensation technique based on the max-min ant system (MMAS) to limit its value, ensure the accuracy of the results, prevent a local optimum, and improve the ACO's capacity for convergence. Furthermore, the ACO is carried out as a GPU kernel function based on the compute unified device architecture (CUDA), which reduces the time required for huge iterations. When used in conjunction with the roulette wheel selection mechanism, FP-ACO is dedicated to finding better solutions and possesses strong search capabilities. The experimental results demonstrate that the speed-up of the algorithm proposed approaches 35 when compared to the effective strategies ACO (ESACO) that operate on CPU and that its running duration is minimized than that of the max-min ant system-roulette wheel method-bitmask tabu (MMAS-RWM-BT) that runs on GPU. Additionally, the approach performs better in terms of run-time and speed-up compared to the other two algorithms, indicating that the suggested FP-ACO is a better fit for solving TSP. To solve large-scale TSPs quickly, the next step is to optimize the GPU memory utilization and thread arrangement, which was also motivated by the trials.

The above mentioned related work didn't address the use of parallel ACO for container allocation. In this study, a novel approach using parallel ant colony optimization technique for containers may be offered which enables the effective scheduling of a large number of containers to improve load balancing and reduce resource execution times while simultaneously increasing resource utilization rates.

III. SEQUENTIAL ANT COLONY OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM FOR CONTAINERS

In a cloud computing environment, resource management and optimization are critical components of container scheduling [2]. In order to maximize effectiveness and satisfy performance requirements, containers are allocated to available resources. The importance of effective container scheduling strategies [3] has increased to ensure that cloud-based applications operate without interruptions. To address these problems, optimization techniques are used to ensure the best possible usage of resources, reduce operating costs, and enhance overall system performance. A basic ACO algorithm emerged from the way ant colonies behave. Ants are social insects that live in colonies or groups. They employ pheromones for communication. Ants from the same colony can smell and obey signals sent by each other through chemicals called pheromones that they produce in the soil. Ants search for the quickest route from the food source to the colony to obtain food. An ant sends out a pheromone in search of food, and other ants follow it to find the quickest path. These are the two main elements to decide the shortest path from the food source to the colony: when more ants choose the shortest route, the concentration of pheromone increases, and the rate of pheromone evaporation to other paths will be decreased. Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) algorithm offers several advantages that make it a powerful tool for solving optimization problems such as their ability to find near-optimal solutions, adaptability to dynamic environments, scalability, and robustness since the pheromone trails and heuristics guide the ants' decision-making, reducing the impact of uncertainties and imperfect problem knowledge. The benefits of ACO make it a useful optimization method with the ability to identify excellent solutions in several areas, such as resource allocation, scheduling, and route optimization. The modified ACO algorithm (MACO) [8] utilizes the main concept of the basic ACO technique for container scheduling in a cloud computing environment. The sequential Modified Ant Colony Optimization (MACO) technique pseudocode is presented in Algorithm 1.

The first step in the algorithm is the initialization step which can be categorized into pheromone level initialization and parameter initialization (Pheromone importance factor (α), Heuristic importance factor (β), Load-balancing factor (γ), and Pheromone evaporation rate (ρ)). Then each ant builds a solution by moving from one node to another under the guidance of pheromone trails and heuristic data. An ant uses the pheromone concentration and a heuristic value to determine the next node in a probabilistic manner at each step. The next step is Pheromone update which is divided into local update and global update. In local update, ants leave modest amounts of pheromones on the paths they take as they move across the solution space to promote exploration while in global update when all ants have built their solutions, adjust the pheromone trails according to the quality of the solution. More pheromones are deposited by better solutions, strengthening those pathways. Then apply evaporation to the pheromone trails, minimizing all pheromone levels by a constant factor. This encourages the algorithm to explore new paths and keeps it from being locked in local optima. Until the allotted number of iterations is achieved, the procedure keeps going.

Algorithm 1 Sequential Modified Ant Colony Optimization (MACO) Algorithm

Input: Number of ants, Maximum number of iterations, VMs list, and containers list.

/Initialization/

Pheromone importance factor (α), Heuristic importance factor (β), Load-balancing factor (γ), and Pheromone evaporation rate (ρ)

Initialization of the pheromone value based Eq. 1:

$$\tau_j(0) = \text{num}_j \times \text{mips}_j + \text{bw}_j \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

/Phase of Iteration/

While Number_of_Iterations are Maximum do

for i = 1 to n ants do

Add a randomly selected virtual machine (VM) to the ant solution list.

end for

While Each Container finds VM to be placed in do

for each ant do

Compute the probability of selecting a VM for allocation of container utilizing Eq. 2

$$p_j^k(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{\tau_j^{\alpha}(t) \cdot CC_k^{\beta}(t, LB_k^j)}{\sum_k \tau_k^{\alpha}(t) \cdot CC_k^{\beta}(t, LB_k^j)} & \text{if } j \in 1, \dots, n \\ 0 & \text{other wise} \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

```

end
Compute the mean time for every ant
if ant_time < best_Placement_Time then
Add the best-Placement to the current solution of ant
end
end
/Update of pheromone /
Evaporate pheromone on all paths:  $\tau = (1 - \text{EvaporationRate}) * \tau$ 
for each ant's solution in the list of solutions do
for each move (assignment) in the solution do
Calculate pheromone increase:  $\Delta\tau = Q / \text{solutionQuality}(\text{ant})$ 
Update the pheromone matrix using Eq. 3
 $\tau_{ij}(t+1) = (1 - \rho) \times \tau_{ij}(t) + \Delta\tau_{ij}$            Eq. 3
end for
end for
Update best_Placement if a better solution is found
Return bestSolution
end
Print the placement array

```

IV. PARALLEL ANT COLONY OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUE FOR CLOUD COMPUTING CONTAINERS

Parallel Ant Colony Optimization (PACO) makes use of the concepts of ACO while boosting performance and scalability through parallel computing. Parallel Ant Colony Optimization (PACO) makes use of parallel computing to enhance the ACO algorithm scalability and performance. Through the division of computational workload among several processors or nodes, PACO can address large-scale optimization problems that are frequently encountered in cloud environments, expedite the convergence process, and investigate several solutions concurrently. ACO algorithm parallelization is very useful in container cloud computing systems where quick decision-making is necessary for the distributed and dynamic nature of resources. The ACO algorithm's execution time may be greatly shortened by utilizing parallelism, which makes it a workable solution for large-scale and dynamic container systems. Key steps in the parallel ACO approach include : The pseudocode of the proposed Parallel Ant Colony Optimization (PACO) scheduling technique for cloud computing containers is presented in Algorithm 2. The proposed algorithm is divided into the following steps:

- Initialization:
 - o Set the initial pheromone levels on each path from container to host by initializing the pheromone matrix T with tiny positive values.
 - o Set the initial values of the heuristic matrix H, which shows whether it is desirable to assign hosts to containers based on resource capacity, and load.
- Parallel Execution:
 - o To enable several ants to operate in parallel, a thread pool containing NumAnts threads is formed.
 - o Based on the pheromone levels (T) and heuristic information (H), each ant builds a solution in parallel by allocating containers to virtual machines in a probabilistic manner.
- Solution Construction:
 - o Every ant computes the probability of associating a container to a virtual machine using Eq. 2
 - o The next virtual machine for every container is selected based on these probabilities.
- Pheromone Update:
 - o Once the ant has constructed a solution, it assesses the solution's suitability.
 - o Parallel updates are made to the pheromone matrix T, with each ant contributing to the pheromone levels according to the quality of its answer. Pheromone is deposited more in higher-quality solutions.

- Synchronization and Convergence:
 - o To provide uniformity throughout all threads, pheromone updates are synchronized.
 - o If any ant during the iteration discovers a better solution, the global best solution is updated.
 - o The algorithm checks to see if it has reached the maximum number of iterations.
- Best Solution Formation:
 - o The nearly optimal container-to-VM allocation is returned based on the best solution discovered during the iterations.

Algorithm 2 Parallel Ant Colony Optimization (PACO) Algorithm for Cloud Computing Containers Allocation

Input: Number of ants, Maximum number of iterations, VMs list and containers list, Pheromone importance factor (α), Heuristic importance factor (β), Load-balancing factor (γ), and Pheromone evaporation rate (ρ)

Output: Optimal or near-optimal container-to-VM allocation

/Initialization/

Initialize pheromone matrix T with small positive values

Initialize heuristic matrix H based on VM resources and container requirements

Initialization of the pheromone value based on Eq. 1

/Phase of Iteration/

While Number_of_Iterations are Maximum do

Initialize thread pool with NumAnts threads

// Create ants and assign each to a thread

For antIndex = 1 to NumAnts do in parallel

Create an ant

Initialize ant's solution to empty set

CurrentVM = Select initial host based on heuristic H

// Construct solution

While there are unscheduled containers do

For each container c do

Calculate probability $p(c, v)$ of assigning container c to VM v

Compute the probability of selecting a VM for allocation of container using Eq. 2

End For

Select next VM h for container c based on probability $p(c, v)$

Update ant's solution with (c -> v)

End While

End For

Evaluate the solution quality (fitness) of each ant's solution

// Update pheromone levels in parallel

For each ant do this in parallel

For each container-host pair (c, h) in ant's solution do

Calculate pheromone increase: $\Delta T(c, v) = Q / \text{solutionQuality}(\text{ant})$

Update pheromone matrix: $T(c, v) = (1 - \text{EvaporationRate}) * T(c, v) + \Delta T(c, v)$

End For

End For

Synchronize pheromone updates across all threads.

End For

Update the global best solution if a better solution is found.

// Check for convergence or maximum iterations

If the convergence criterion is met or iteration == MaxIterations then

Break

End If

End For

```
Return BestSolution
end for
sendNow (container ID, virtual machine ID)
```

V. IMPLEMENTATION AND SIMULATION RESULTS

This section verifies the suggested allocation strategies, which are subsequently assessed by the Container Cloud Sim simulator.

Implementation Environment

In order to enable simulation, modeling, and experimentation of developing the infrastructures and application services of cloud computing. Container Cloud Sim [13] provides support for modeling and simulating cloud computing infrastructures using containers concerning controlling the CPU, memory, and storage resources of hosts, virtual machines (VMs), containers, and data centers. More specifically, it ought to include basic features like managing application execution within containers, dynamically monitoring system status, and assigning virtual machines to containers. Resource allocation to virtual machines and containers is governed by container scheduling policies, which can be expanded to accommodate the testing of novel approaches so it allows researchers to compare and plug in new scheduling and provisioning policies for containers.

Parameter setting

A virtualized cloud architecture including numerous nodes, each hosting multiple containers running a combination of CPU, memory, and I/O-bound applications, makes up the simulation environment. We set the number of iterations to 10, number of hosts to 20 and the number of VMs to 50. Two implementations of the ACO algorithm exist: the sequential version we implement the Modified Ant Colony Optimization (MACO) algorithm [8] and the proposed parallel version. The most important parameters that affect the results of the proposed algorithm are:

- Alpha (α): This parameter regulates how much pheromone affects the ants' ability to make decisions. The ants are more dependent on the pheromone trail when the value is higher. Typically its value ranges between 1 and 2. If the ants are not sufficiently following the pheromone trail, start with 1.0 and increase.
- Beta (β): This parameter regulates how much the heuristic data—such as cost or distance—influences the ants' decision-making. An increased value indicates that the ants depend more on heuristic data than on pheromones. Typically it ranges from 1 to 5. Values of 2.0 to 3.0 are typical. Depending on how much of an impact you want the heuristic information to have over the pheromone, start with 2.0 and make adjustments.
- Pheromone Evaporation (γ): The pheromone trail's evaporation rate is determined by this parameter. While a low rate can result in slow convergence, a high rate keeps the algorithm from converging too rapidly to a bad solution. Typically it ranges from 0.1 to 0.5.

The setting of the parameters of the proposed algorithm that explore the best performance is illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1. ACO Parameter Setting

Parameter	Value
Number of Ants	100
Alpha	1
Beta	2
Evaporation rate	0.4

Experimental results

To add parallelization for the Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) using threads, we will utilize Java's Thread class to parallelize the ACO operations across different threads. We create a runnable task for each ant in the colony and execute them concurrently. This approach will speed up the process of finding optimal VM and container allocations. By computing solutions concurrently across numerous threads, this method shortens the ACO algorithm's overall runtime. The number of threads can be dynamically changed in accordance with available

resources. Figure 2 shows that the execution time decreased linearly as the number of threads increased. As the number of threads increases, the execution time is drastically reduced. Increased processing resources should enable the task to be divided and processed concurrently, so the execution time should decrease as the number of threads rises. When more threads are added, execution times normally decrease significantly, as shown in Figure 2. Due to communication overhead, thread synchronization, and contention for shared resources the graph was flattened to high values of threads, reducing the efficiency gains from additional threads. When more threads are added, the execution time cannot be greatly decreased in the end and might even increase in certain situations as a result of these overheads.

Figure 2: Execution time in seconds vs. number of threads

The speedup achieved by the proposed PACO algorithm against the number of threads used is presented in Fig. 3. Ideally, as the number of threads increases, the speedup should linearly increase, approaching a value equal to the number of threads, reflecting perfect parallelization. However, in practice, Figure 3 shows a sub-linear curve due to various overheads like thread synchronization, communication, and resource contention. Initially, the speedup increases rapidly with the number of threads, but as more threads are added, the curve tends to flatten out, illustrating diminishing returns. This flattening occurs because, beyond a certain point, the overhead costs outweigh the benefits of additional parallelism, resulting in limited further speedup.

Figure 3: Speedup

Figure 4 illustrates the relative improvement of the execution time of the PACO and MACO w.r.t FCFS across all cloudlets. A negative value of the relative execution time indicates better performance. The PACO performs better than the MACO and FCFS algorithms. The best improvement for the proposed algorithm is when number of cloudlets is 500. The worst value of PACO is when the number of cloudlets is 400 and 200.

Figure 4: The relative improvement in execution time w.r.t FCFS

Figure 5 shows the throughput of the proposed PACO, MACO, and FCFS algorithm versus the number of cloudlets. As the number of cloudlets increased the throughput increased. PACO outperforms the MACO and FCFS algorithms.

Figure 5: Throughput

VI. CONCLUSION

The application of a parallel Ant Colony Optimization (PACO) algorithm shows great promise for improving computational efficiency in complicated optimization problems, like cloud resource allocation. By dividing the workload among several threads, PACO efficiently shortens the execution time and enhances the quality of the solution by enabling a more thorough exploration of the solution space in a shorter amount of time. The findings show that although parallelization provides significant speedup and scalability benefits, the performance gains are ultimately limited by factors like communication overhead and synchronization costs. These conclusions emphasize the significance of carefully balancing the number of threads and managing computational resources to maximize the efficiency of parallel algorithms. To further improve speed and scalability in dynamic and large-scale contexts, future work should investigate more sophisticated parallelization schemes, adaptive thread management, and hybrid approaches combining PACO with other optimization techniques.

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